

Visualizations for the Evolution of Variant-Rich Systems: A Systematic Mapping Study

Raul Medeiros¹, Jabier Martinez², Oscar Díaz¹, Jean-Rémy Falleri³

¹University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), San Sebastian, Spain

²Tecnalia, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Derio, Spain

³LaBRI, UMR 5800, F-33400, IUF, Talence, France

Gallery of primary sources

[S2] L. Montalvillo, O. Díaz, T. Fogdal, Reducing coordination overhead in SPLs: peering in on peers, in: SPLC, ACM, 2018, pp. 110–120.

GitHub, Inc. [US] | https://github.com/letimome/WeatherStation-SPLC18/tree/productDenmark

This repository | Search | Pull requests | Issues | Marketplace | Explore

letimome / WeatherStation-SPLC18

Code | Issues 16 | Pull requests 0 | Projects 5 | Wiki | Insights | Settings

Web-based Weather Station SPL

Add topics

5 commits | 7 branches | 4 releases | 1 contributor

Peering bar

WindSpeed (35 %) | English (30 %) | AirPressure (15 %) | Gale (10 %) | Temperature (10 %)

Branch: productDenmark | New pull request | Create new file | Upload files | Find file | Clone or download

This branch is 4 commits ahead of master. | Pull request | Compare

letimome multiple issues: #13 #14 #15 | Latest commit 27bac1 8 days ago

.settings | first commit | 14 days ago

Figure 3. Visualization of three products variability at source code level and clones of a specific file

[S4] J. Martinez, T. Ziadi, R. Mazo, T. F. Bissyandé, J. Klein, Y. L. Traon, Feature relations graphs: A visualisation paradigm for feature constraints in software product lines, in: VISSOFT, IEEE Computer Society, 2014, pp. 50–59.

Fig. 6: Screenshot of FRoGs visualisation tool focusing on the PBSAutomatic feature of the Electric Parking Brake SPL

Figure 2: Visualization of Variance in Presence

Figure 3: Hierarchical Representation of Variances

Figure 4: Results Subsystem protocols

[S8] A. Murashkin, M. Antkiewicz, D. Rayside, K. Czarnecki, Visualization and exploration of optimal variants in product line engineering, in: SPLC, ACM, 2013, pp. 111–115.

Fig. 3. Our approach is integrated in the feature-oriented development environment FORCE². Suggested feature-level dependencies and interactions are shown in the feature model (middle-right part). For the selected feature `crane` all the dependencies and interactions to other features are shown. Different line colors and line types are used to distinguish different types of dependencies or interactions (e.g., red dashed lines for def-use dependencies and turquoise lines for read-read interactions). Engineers can select features to

Fig. 9. An excerpt of the evolution of dependencies and interactions from KePlast version 1 to version 53 visualized using the feature dependency evolution matrix. The changes in version 53 focus on the features `Injection`, `Inject` and `Plast`. The changes introduced new status variables in the feature `Injection` which cause def-use dependencies and write-write, write-read and read-read interactions between the features. Most of the new dependencies and interactions were found between the features `Inject` and `Plast`.

Figure 4: Proposed interactive visualization tool. On the left criteria pane, the user sets (a) the states or the weights of criterion values and (b) the importance of criteria. On the right product pane, products are dynamically listed (c) according to corresponding states. They are ordered according to user interactions: toggling value glyphs, dragging colored sliders, (e) adjusting threshold slider. The information of confidence level is (d) expressed as bar charts, and its details are (f) represented as stacked bar charts.

Figure 4: View for relationships of features to files

Figure 5: View for relationships of features to folders

Feature	Config	DB	Network
MobilePhone	Green	Green	Red
GPS	Green	Green	Green
Resolution	Green	Red	Red
Basic	Green	Green	Green
HD	Green	Green	Green
Calls	Green	Green	Green
Media	Green	Red	Red
Camera	Green	Green	Green
MP3	Green	Red	Red
EarPhone	Green	Green	Green
Memory	Green	Red	Green
Battery	Red	Green	Red

Figure 6: Common features between projects

Figure 7: Features tangled with *Camera*

Figure 10: Experimental view showing a feature's history

Fig. 2: Visualization of Dependencies of DPL

Fig. 3: Visualization of Derivatives ZipMe

Fig. 4: Visualization of Modules of VOD with selected feature CHANGESERVER

Fig. 5: Visualization of Artifacts of DPL

Figure 6. Three text files from Fig. 2 with visualization of element status. The corresponding occurrence matrices are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 8. Hierarchical aggregation of occurrence matrices and bar diagrams for four variants of a folder containing three files. The shared category was split into shared by 3 and shared by 2, using two distinct colors, for better insight into variability distribution

Fig. 4. A screenshot of the example case in COVAMOF-VS. This figure shows some of the variation points and dependencies that are involved to provide the variability of the example case we discussed in section 3.

[S17] J. Martinez, T. Ziadi, J. Klein, Y. L. Traon, Identifying and visualising commonality and variability in model variants, in: ECMFA, Vol. 8569 of Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer, 2014, pp. 117–131.

Fig. 7. Vending Machine SCT Model variants comparison

[S18] D. Sellier, M. Mannion, Visualizing product line requirement selection decisions, in: SPLC (2), Kindai Kagaku Sha Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan, 2007, pp. 109–118.

Figure 4. V-Visualise and decision model visualisation

Figure 5. V-Visualise and inter-dependency visualisation

Fig. 7 Screen Shot of the ATF Tree View

Fig. 13 Feature Model Evolution

Fig. 11 Impacted Artefacts From Radial View.

Fig. 12 Room with Security Product Evolution

Fig. 10 View of the Initial Trace Set (top part) and enlarged view of some nodes (bottom part)

Fig. 14 Two Products Comparison

Fig. 4: Available interactions on a feature

Fig. 7: Visualization of the Yourcast SPL

Fig. 3. The QBS unified requirements concept lattice

Fig. 5. The 'data feeds' lattice without req 51 (left) or without req 52 (right) with variabilization line drawn

a) All tf

b) Variant 1 tf

Block 0

Block 1

Block 2

Block 3

Block 4

Block 5

Figure 3: Word cloud examples of vending machine variants

Figure 1. Overview of ArchFeature

Figure 3: OPLA-Tool v2.0 user interaction

Movement		
	Δ Scattering	Δ Size
A	+90%	+25%
B	-8%	-10%

varApp XML Document Variabilization and Reconfiguration Application

Project Model Root Document Upload Root Document Wrap element Vary attribute Wrap text Delete variant Delete variation point (keep variant) Compare Document Configuration

Variability Model

- PPU
 - + < [1..1]
 - o VP slide: Slide
 - o VP conveyor: SortingConveyor
 - crane: Crane
 - + vacuumgripper: VacuumGripper
 - + liftingcylinder: LiftingCylinder
 - turningtable: TurningTable
 - o positions:xs:integer= VP 3
 - + emotor: (EMotorEU)
 - positiondetectiondiscrete: (ArrayOfContactSwitches)
 - + VP Position Detection#_uJOyAGKfEem8ua0h5pRJpw
 - o +ArrayOfContactSwitches base_Class: PositionDet
 - o +PotentiometerDiscretization base_Class: Position
 - o stack: Stack

Root Document

Load root files/plcopen-xml/root.xml

```
+ <pou TurningTable> Attr:  
+ <interface>  
+ <localVars>  
+ <variable Motor> Attr:  
+ VP Position Detection#_uJOyAGKfEem8ua0h5pRJpw  
+ V (_8P0qwF-VEemyzbirsO7-9g)  
+ <variable Potentiometer> Attr:  
+ V (_4Y8f0F-VEemyzbirsO7-9g)  
+ <variable AtStack> Attr:  
+ VP Conveyor#_2IUaoF-NEemyzbirsO7-9g  
+ V (0)  
+ <variable AtRamp> Attr:  
+ V (1)  
+ <variable AtConveyor> Attr:  
+ <variable AtStamp> Attr:
```

powered by

VarApp - © AIS; Markus Male

[S28] A. Schlie, K. Rosiak, O. Urbaniak, I. Schaefer, B. Vogel-Heuser, Analyzing variability in automation software with the variability analysis toolkit, in: SPLC (B), ACM, 2019, pp. 89:1–89:8.

The screenshot shows the Variability Analysis Toolkit interface. The window title is "Variability Analysis Toolkit". The menu bar includes "File", "Window", "Help", and "Export". The toolbar contains icons for project management and a "PerspectiveSwitch" dropdown set to "default".

The interface is divided into several panes:

- Project Explorer (left):** Shows a tree view of the project structure. It includes folders for "01 Models", "02 Metrics", "03 Results", "04 FamilyModels", and "05 FeatureModels". A red number "2" is placed next to this pane.
- Compare Engine (bottom left):** Contains controls for "SourceModel", "TargetModel", "Metric", "Matching" (with a "Sorting Matcher" dropdown), "WeightedCompare", and a "Compare" button. A red number "1" is placed above this pane.
- Metric Manager (top right):** Displays a list of metrics for the selected model "Advanced_Simple_Family_Model". The metrics include MAIN, MicroSwitch, MonostableCylinder, Motor, OperationPanel, TurningTable, VacuumGripper, VacuumSwitch, Valve, Crane, Stack, PPU, and InductiveSensor. A red number "3" is placed next to this list.
- Console (bottom right):** Shows a table of attributes. A red number "4" is placed above the table, with a red arrow pointing down to the table.

Name	Type
PROJECT ATTRIBUTES	Container
Number of POU's	PROJECT ATTRIBUTES
Names - Levenshtein Distance	PROJECT ATTRIBUTES
Names of Global Variables	PROJECT ATTRIBUTES
Data Type of Global Variables	PROJECT ATTRIBUTES
Number of Global Variables	PROJECT ATTRIBUTES
ACTION ATTRIBUTES	Container
POU ATTRIBUTES	Container
VARIABLE ATTRIBUTES	Container
LANGUAGE ATTRIBUTES	Container

[S29] D. H. Carmo, S. T. Carvalho, L. G. P. Murta, O. Loques, Runtime monitoring and auditing of self-adaptive systems (S), in: SEKE, Knowledge Systems Institute Graduate School, 2013, pp. 731–736.

Figure 4 Architecture Configuration Diff view

Context and feature model visualisation

A visualisation tool that shows the context and feature model

Filters

GoJS 1.8 evaluation (c) 1998-2018 Northwoods Software Not for distribution or production use northwoods.com

Predefined views

- Complete mode
- Active mode
- Inactive mode
- Active contexts mode
- Active features mode
- Active classes mode

Customized views

Contexts	Contexts-Features	Features	Features-Code	Code
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated contexts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> active dependencies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Activated features	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> dependencies with active features	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> impacted classes
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Inactivated contexts	<input type="checkbox"/> inactive dependencies	<input type="checkbox"/> Inactivated features	<input type="checkbox"/> dependencies with inactive features	<input type="checkbox"/> non-impacted classes
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> active dependencies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> labels	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> active dependencies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> labels	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> inactive dependencies		<input type="checkbox"/> inactive dependencies		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> labels		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> labels		

Configuration

Color Skins: Standard, Black-and-white

Step-by-step:

Time between each refresh (sec.):

Figure 4: Demarcation of feature locations in source code

Figure 5: Feature-file trace view

Figure 6: Feature-folder trace view

Figure 7: Visualization of an in-file annotation

Figure 4: Product Evolution Tree for Dataset 2

[S34] M. Ribeiro, T. Toledo, J. Winther, C. Brabrand, P. Borba, Emergo: a tool for improving maintainability of preprocessor-based product lines, in: OSD (Companion), ACM, 2012, pp. 23–26.

The screenshot shows the Eclipse IDE with the following components:

- Left Panel (Project Explorer):** Shows the project structure with folders for Kernel, MobileMedia, and src. The src folder contains several Java files including AbstractController.java, AlbumListScreen.java, MediaController.java, PhotoViewController.java, PhotoViewScreen.java, and SmsSenderController.java.
- Main Editor:** Displays the source code of MediaController.java. The code includes a class declaration, a private field, and a public method showImage(int id) with preprocessor directives for (COPY) and (SMS).
- Emergo Graph View:** Shows a dependency graph with three nodes: smscontroller.setNextController(nextcontroller);, AbstractController nextcontroller = this;, and controller.setNextController(nextcontroller);. Arrows indicate dependencies, with labels (ICOPY & SMS) and (COPY).
- Emergo Table View:** Lists 2 items with the following details:

Description	Configuration	Location	Feature	Resource
AbstractController nextcontroller = this;	(ICOPY & SMS)	line 21	(SMS)	MediaController.java
AbstractController nextcontroller = this;	(COPY)	line 14	(COPY)	MediaController.java

Figure 5: The *vp*-s with variants for the selected zone of interest in Figure 4

Fig. 2. Covering array example of GPL

Fig. 3. Bubble and heatmap representation of covering array of GPL

Fig. 4. Tree map representation of coverage increment for GPL

[S37] T. H. B. de Oliveira, M. Becker, E. Y. Nakagawa, Supporting the analysis of bug prevalence in software product lines with product genealogy, in: SPLC (1), ACM, 2012, pp. 181–185.

Figure 3: Concept lattice for the running example.

Figure 4: Categorizing the concept lattice.

[S39] T. F. L. de Medeiros, E. S. de Almeida, S. R. de Lemos Meira, Codescoping: A source code based tool to software product lines scoping, in: EUROMICRO-SEAA, IEEE Computer Society, 2012, pp. 101–104.

The figure displays four screenshots of the CodeScoping tool interface, illustrating its functionality in software product lines scoping.

Screenshot 1 (Top Left): Shows the 'Product Map' tab. A table compares features across three products: NotepadA, NotepadB, and NotepadC. The 'UndoRedo' feature is highlighted in blue, indicating a 100.00% similarity ratio. Other features like 'Port_Format', 'Clipboard', 'Find', 'Save_File', 'SelectAll', 'LineWrap', 'Print', 'New_File', and 'Open_File' have similarity ratios ranging from 23.81% to 43.06%.

Feature	NotepadA	NotepadB	NotepadC	Similarity Ratio (%)
Port_Format	✓	✓	✓	34.34
Clipboard	✓	✓	✓	43.06
Find	✓	✗	✗	-
Save_File	✓	✓	✓	66.33
UndoRedo	✓	✓	✓	100.00
SelectAll	✗	✓	✗	64.29
LineWrap	✗	✓	✗	-
Print	✓	✗	✗	23.81
New_File	✓	✓	✓	-
Open_File	✓	✓	✓	42.75

Screenshot 2 (Top Right): Shows the 'Choose a configuration for the feature UndoRedo' dialog. It lists three configurations, all with a similarity ratio of 66.06%. Each configuration is composed of NotepadA and NotepadC.

Screenshot 3 (Middle Right): Shows the 'Feature UndoRedo (69.33%)' diagram. It is a network graph where nodes represent products (NotepadA, NotepadB, NotepadC) and edges represent dependencies. NotepadA and NotepadC are highlighted in red and blue circles, respectively, while NotepadB is highlighted in green.

Screenshot 4 (Bottom Left): Shows the 'Source Code' tab. It displays the source code for the 'UndoAction' class in NotepadA (left) and NotepadC (right). The code is highlighted in yellow, and the differences between the two versions are clearly visible. The 'UndoAction' class in NotepadA has a 'protected void update()' method, while the version in NotepadC has a 'protected void update()' method that calls 'notepad.undo.redoAction.update()'.

Figure 3. CodeScoping Screenshots

[S40] R. Rabiser, D. Dhungana, W. Heider, P. Grünbacher, Flexibility and end-user support in model-based product line tools, in: EUROMICRO-SEAA, IEEE Computer Society, 2009, pp. 508–511

[S41] K. Wnuk, B. Regnell, L. Karlsson, What happened to our features? visualization and understanding of scope change dynamics in a large-scale industrial setting, in: RE, IEEE Computer Society, 2009, pp. 89–98.

Figure 1- Feature Survival Chart for project A.